

CFD Prediction of Cavitation Inception on Marine Propellers

Keun-Woo Shin^{1,*}, Mina Kim², Byoung-Kwon Ahn² and Jens Ring Nielsen¹

¹ Propeller & Aft Ship – R&D Department, Everllence, Frederikshavn, Denmark

² Department of Autonomous Vehicle System Engineering, Chungnam National University, Daejeon, Korea

Abstract. Cavitation-free operation up to a certain ship speed is required for special-purpose ships to fulfill assigned missions due to noise signals and hull pressure pulses amplified by cavitating flows from marine propellers. In order to delay cavitation inception, it is necessary to make accurate predictions of cavitation inception speeds on the suction and pressure sides of a propeller blade in a range of operating conditions. Unsteady cavitation simulations are carried out by DES with a multiphase flow model on a 4-bladed propeller of a twin-screw ship in the behind-hull condition for predicting a cavity volume at an inception speed. Cavitation variation with respect to the blade position is validated against experimental results from a large-size cavitation tunnel including a hull model in the design condition. A threshold range of the maximum cavity volume for determining cavitation inception is derived through the validation. A cavitation diagram is prepared by estimating inception curves for both the sides of the blade through CFD simulations in the fully-wetted condition. By comparing the numerically estimated cavitation diagram with experimental measurements, an equivalent cavity volume corresponding to the computational cell volume with local pressure below the vapor pressure is estimated for predicting inception curves. The numerical prediction method of inception curves can be practically used for delaying cavitation inception in a ship propeller design process.

Keywords: *ship propeller, cavitation, cavitation inception, tip vortex cavitation, CFD*

1 Introduction

It is important to predict and delay cavitation inception on marine propellers because hull pressure pulses and noise signals are amplified by more than an order of magnitude when cavitation inception occurs [1, 2]. Cavitation-free sailings are required for special-purpose ships engaged in ocean research, fishery, military operations to fulfill assigned missions. Cargo safety and comfort onboard are enhanced by suppressing cavitation and reducing hull pressure pulse levels especially on ships carrying high-value goods and passengers.

Tip vortex cavitation (TVC) is often the first cavitation type observed on marine propellers at the lowest inception speed. A turbulent viscous flow solver is necessary to simulate TVC, whereas sheet cavitation can be predicted to a certain degree by inviscid flow methods like potential flow method, vortex lattice method. TVC and high-order pressure pulses have been predicted by a hybrid method consisting of a viscous flow method on hull flow, a potential flow method on propeller flow and an empirical model on TVC, but it has limitations in taking into account interactive vortex dynamics due to an iterative setup of the TVC model based on separate viscous flow simulations or experimental results [3]. The large extent of TVC on a marine propeller in the open-water condition has been simulated by a Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) solver with different turbulence models [4]. The vortex dynamics of TVC in the behind-hull condition has been simulated by detached-eddy simulation (DES) and large-eddy simulation (LES) solvers with an adaptive grid [5, 6].

It is challenging to make numerical predictions of TVC inception, as it has a large variation depending on test conditions like gas content, turbulent intensity and surface roughness in cavitation tunnel tests. The inception of TVC on an elliptic hydrofoil has been predicted by RANS simulations for different Reynolds numbers in an agreement with experimental results [7]. The TVC inception on a marine propeller in the behind-hull condition has been simulated by DES to derive a threshold value of the maximum cavity volume for determining TVC inception [8].

In this study, the inception of TVC and sheet cavitation on both blade sides of a marine propeller is predicted by DES in the behind-hull condition for estimating inception curves on a diagram of the advance ratio J and the cavitation number σ

* Correspondence to: keun.shin@everllence.com

$$J = \frac{V_S \cdot (1 - w)}{N \cdot D}, \sigma = \frac{P_{Atm} + \rho \cdot g \cdot h - P_V}{0.5 \cdot \rho \cdot V_\infty^2} \quad (1)$$

where V_S is the ship speed, w is the effective wake fraction, N is the propeller speed, D is the propeller diameter, P_{Atm} is the atmospheric pressure, ρ is the water density, g is the gravitational acceleration, h is the propeller shaft submergence depth, P_V is the vapor pressure and V_∞ is the reference velocity.

Two approaches are introduced to predict an inception point along an operation curve by cavitation simulations and to estimate inception curves of TVC, sheet cavitation and leading-edge (LE) vortex cavitation by fully-wetted flow simulations. The numerical prediction for a cavitation inception diagram is validated against cavitation tunnel test results and the criteria for determining cavitation inception are established through the validation. The scope of this study is limited to cavitation inception prediction in model scale. Further investigations in future are necessary for making predictions of full-scale cavitation inception due to water quality impact and scale effects related to TVC.

2 CFD setup

Unsteady simulations are carried out by the DES solver of the commercial CFD software StarCCM+ with the Schnerr-Sauer cavitation model, that is, an interphase mass transfer model based on the asymptotic Rayleigh-Plesset equation, and the VOF (volume-of-fluid) method for multiphase flow modeling. The CFD method adopted in this study for propeller cavitation simulations in the behind-hull condition has been validated against cavitation tunnel test results for different types of cavitation and cavitation-related issues [9, 10]. A 4-bladed controllable-pitch propeller designed for a twin-screw open-shaft ship is considered as a test case. It has been tested in the large cavitation tunnel of SSPA including the hull model.

Figure 1. (a) computational domain with volumetric grid on a vertical section, (b) surface grid on propeller and rudder models

Figure 2. Nominal hull wake field with blade positions for suction- (red dotted line) and pressure-side (green dashed line) cavitation inception: contour plot – axial wake, vector plot – transverse wake

CFD simulations are conducted in model scale by following the experimental condition. As shown in Figure 1, a cylindrical computational domain around propeller and rudder models is prepared with extents of $3.6 \cdot D$ upstream, $7.2 \cdot D$ downstream and $4.8 \cdot D$ radially from the propeller center. The domain size is set to simulate propeller flows without numerical disturbance from boundary conditions according to the investigation on the influence of the computational domain size on propeller thrust and torque [13]. A subdomain is defined around the propeller model for modeling propeller rotations by the sliding grid and the rigid body motion. The propeller shaft is extended to the inlet boundary with the slip wall boundary condition.

A trimmed hexahedral grid is generated in the computational domain. The surface grid size is set to $\Delta x = 0.1\% \cdot D - 0.2\% \cdot D$ on the overall blade and hub and it is refined to $0.05\% \cdot D - 0.1\% \cdot D$ along the blade edges. Boundary-layer flows are resolved by the prism-layer grid resulting in non-dimensional first-cell heights of $y^+ < 1$ on average. A relatively fine volumetric grid of $\Delta x \approx 0.1\% \cdot D$ is applied to the outer-radius blade region where most cavitation is shown. The volumetric grid on the way from the inlet to the propeller is refined to avoid numerical dissipation of hull wake applied to the propeller inflow. The computational setup for unsteady cavitation simulations has been verified with the time step and the grid size and it has shown consistent results in the overall sheet cavitation extent [14].

A hydrostatic pressure distribution with the reference pressure P_∞ at the propeller shaft axis is applied to the initial condition and the outlet boundary. P_∞ is adjusted according to the considered value of σ

$$P_\infty = 0.5 \cdot \rho \cdot V_\infty^2 \cdot \sigma + P_V \quad (2)$$

A nominal hull wake field measured in a towing tank test is applied to the propeller inflow instead of including a hull model. In Figure 2, the hull wake field seen from aft on the starboard side shows axial wake behind the two struts and upward flows. The axial hull wake component adjusted by a ratio of the effective wake fraction to the nominal one is applied to the inlet boundary as a non-uniform velocity distribution. The transverse hull wake consisting of radial and tangential components is modelled by momentum sources applied $0.35 \cdot D - 0.4 \cdot D$ upstream from the propeller plane outside the rotating subdomain [11]. Momentum source strengths are iteratively calibrated by numerical tests made in the computational domain without the propeller model.

3 CFD cavitation simulation

The inception curves from the cavitation tunnel tests are shown in Figure 3. It is the model-scale inception curves of TVC not scaled by McCormick's law [12] for considering full-scale Reynolds number. An operation curve intersects with the inception curve of suction-side TVC at Condition 1 of $J = 0.65$ and $\sigma = 9.65$ corresponding to a ship speed V_{S0} , where J is the advance. When the ship speed is increased further from V_{S0} , the starting point of cavitation is moved down from the tip along LE and it is deemed to be the inception of sheet cavitation. Cavitation simulation at Condition 1 is validated against the experimental results and a threshold value of the maximum cavity volume is estimated for determining the inception of TVC.

Figure 3. Cavitation inception diagram from cavitation tunnel tests

In Figure 4, the CFD cavitation simulation is compared with the experimental result at the inception of TVC on the suction side of the blade. TVC is in a developed stage rather than in an initial stage because cavitation needs to be developed to be constant and stable on at least half of the blades until it is considered as inception. In CFD, cavitation interfaces indicated by light and dark blue contours are defined by the iso-surfaces of vapor volume fractions 10% and 50%, respectively. CFD shows a good agreement with the experimental result in the shape and extent of TVC. The experiment shows TVC from the blade position of $\theta = 20^\circ$, whereas cavitation starts earlier at LE of about $0.9 \cdot R$ in CFD and it is converted into TVC from $\theta \approx 10^\circ$.

In Figure 5, the variation of the cavity volume V_{Cav} around a blade in CFD simulation is presented with respect to the blade position. Cavitation starts and grows from $\theta = -20^\circ$ and the maximum cavity volume of $V_{Cav,Max0} = 23.1 \text{ mm}^3$ is reached at $\theta \approx 40^\circ$. TVC decays gradually at $\theta = 60 - 120^\circ$. There is no distinctive fluctuation of V_{Cav} except near the complete desinence of TVC at $\theta = 90 - 120^\circ$. The maximum cavity volume $V_{Cav,Max0}$ can be used as a threshold value for determining cavitation inception.

It is recommended to use a certain range of threshold values because $V_{Cav,Max}$ can vary depending on single-blade area, blade tip shape and turbulence flow properties. A threshold range with a margin of $\pm 8 \text{ mm}^3$ from $V_{Cav,Max}$ is set based on the experience in CFD predictions of TVC inception for other propeller cases. Cavitation tunnel tests on elliptic hydrofoils have shown cavity volume fluctuations of $5 - 12 \text{ mm}^3$ from the mean value at TVC inception when the measurement of the projected cavity area is converted into a cavity volume [2].

Figure 4. Cavitation on the suction side of the blade in cavitation tunnel test and CFD at Condition 1

Figure 5. Cavity volume around a blade with respect to the blade position in CFD cavitation simulation at Condition 1

4 Cavitation inception diagram

When a cavitation inception speed (CIS) on an operation curve is predicted for a new propeller design, cavitation simulations are carried out on 2 – 3 operation points to have a threshold range located between calculated values of $V_{Cav,Max}$ and to interpolate CIS. If cavitation simulations are used for estimating cavitation inception curves, it is too time-consuming to be adopted in a propeller design phase because 10 – 20 simulations need to be run for predicting inception points in 5 – 6 loading conditions. Therefore, fully-wetted flow simulations are made for estimating three inception curves on suction-side TVC, sheet cavitation and pressure-side LE vortex cavitation by intentionally increasing the reference pressure enough to incur no cavitation.

Figure 6. Distribution of pressure coefficient on the suction and pressure sides of the blade in CFD simulation for $J = 0.95$

Figure 7. Equivalent cavity volume in fully-wetted flow simulations for $J = 0.69$ and 0.95

CFD simulations are made for 6 loading conditions in $J = 0.63 - 1.05$. In Figure 6, the distribution of pressure coefficient C_p on the suction and pressure sides of the blade in CFD simulation for $J = 0.95$ is presented, where

$C_P = (P - P_\infty)/(0.5 \cdot \rho \cdot V_\infty^2)$. As $J = 0.95$ is a low loading condition, the minimum pressure is lower on the pressure side than on the suction side and thus the pressure-side cavitation is shown earlier. The surface area with $C_P \leq -3.0$ is the largest at $\theta = 43^\circ$ and 250° on the suction and pressure sides, respectively, which corresponds to the blade positions showing the minimum pressure. As the minimum pointwise pressure can be affected by cell quality, it can be better to look at the surface area of neighboring cells within a certain pressure range. These two blade positions are considered for estimating cavitation inception.

The volume of cells V_{eCav} with $C_P \leq -\sigma$ corresponding to local pressure below the vapor pressure is calculated by varying the value of σ . As it is based on fully-wetted flow simulations, V_{eCav} with $C_P \leq -\sigma$ is equivalent to the cavity volume simply from a pressure distribution without cavitation dynamics like cavity shedding, cavity-vortex interaction, cavity coalescence and break-up. In Figure 7, the equivalent cavity distributions are presented for $V_{eCav} = 0.1 - 100 \text{ mm}^3$.

When the equivalent cavity of suction-side TVC is compared to the actual ones in Figure 4, it is developed on the tip surface without a 3-dimensional vortex shape for $V_{eCav} = 0.1 - 10 \text{ mm}^3$ and it is extended over the tip without a spiral pattern for $V_{eCav} = 100 \text{ mm}^3$. The equivalent cavity for suction-side sheet cavitation excluding the volume at the tip and downstream is developed like LE sheet cavitation and it is distributed over a large area due to a small thickness. The pressure-side cavitation is formed along LE from $0.6 \cdot R - 0.7 \cdot R$ and it is detached from the surface in a vortex form at $0.84 \cdot R$ because pressure is reversed to have low pressure on the pressure side at inner radii below $0.8 \cdot R$ and low pressure is kept on the suction side at the tip.

Figure 8. Cavitation inception curves from cavitation tunnel tests and CFD: (a) suction-side TVC, (b) suction-side sheet cavitation, (c) pressure-side LE vortex cavitation and (d) inception diagram

In Figure 8, cavitation inception curves are prepared by interpolating σ for $V_{eCav} = 0.1 - 100 \text{ mm}^3$. The CFD curves for $V_{eCav} = 1 \text{ mm}^3$ are closer to the experimental results for all three types of cavitation. The equivalent cavity volume of $V_{eCav} = 1 \text{ mm}^3$ is much smaller than the threshold range of $V_{Cav} = 15 - 30 \text{ mm}^3$ from the cavitating flow simulation because cavity convection and cavity-vortex interaction are neglected to underpredict a low

pressure region corresponding to the equivalent cavity volume. When a cavity is transported by convection and vortex flows are altered by cavity in the cavitating flow simulation, a cavity can be more extended than in the fully-wetted flow simulation. The difference between the equivalent cavity in the fully-wetted flow simulation and the actual cavity in the cavitating flow simulation becomes larger, as cavitation is further developed for a lower cavitation number after cavitation inception. Since the difference is relatively small for the incipient cavitation number, fully-wetted flow simulations can be used as a practical alternative with lower computational effort.

The CFD curves of suction-side TVC and pressure-side LE vortex cavitation show a good agreement with the experimental result, but there are deviations at $J = 0.65 - 0.70$ due to LE vortex separation in a high loading for suction-side TVC and at $J = 0.85 - 0.90$ due to a reversed stagnation point for pressure-side cavitation. The CFD curve of suction-side sheet cavitation have a difference in the slope and so the deviation gets larger at $J \geq 0.7$. While the CFD curves of suction-side TVC and sheet cavitation are almost parallel, the slope for sheet cavitation is noticeably higher than that for TVC in the experimental result. The CFD curves of suction-side TVC and sheet cavitation have lower slopes for $V_{eCav} = 10 - 100 \text{ mm}^3$ than $= 0.1 - 1 \text{ mm}^3$. The small difference between the CFD curves of suction-side TVC for $V_{eCav} = 0.1$ and 1 mm^3 indicates high pressure gradients at the tip.

In Figure 8 (d), the CFD inception curves of all the cavitation types for $V_{eCav} = 1 \text{ mm}^3$ are plotted together with the experimental result. The intersection point of the two curves of suction-side TVC and pressure-side LE vortex cavitation is an optimum position for the highest CIS. The CFD estimation shows acceptable accuracy in predicting the optimum position in spite of slight overprediction of σ so that it can be practically used to optimize a propeller design for increasing CIS. As the operation curve is inclined towards the suction-side cavitation inception curve at a high value of σ , it is advisable to aim at a point with a distance from the optimum position towards a lower value of J in considering CIS in full scale because the scope of the current study is limited to model-scale cavitation inception. When a model-scale inception curve is scaled by McCormick's law, it is moved up towards to a higher value of σ . It is desirable to have a larger margin from pressure-side cavitation because of its erosion risk.

5 Conclusion

An unsteady cavitation simulations on a marine propeller in the behind-hull condition is carried out by DES with a multiphase flow model for a condition showing cavitation inception. A threshold range for determining cavitation inception is derived through the validation of the cavitation simulation against a cavitation tunnel test result. CIS on an operation curve can be predicted by running 2 – 3 unsteady cavitation simulations and interpolating it with respect to the maximum cavity volume.

Fully-wetted flow simulations are made for predicting inception curves of different types of propeller cavitation in blade positions showing the minimum pressure on each side of the blade. The CFD inception curves for an equivalent cavity volume corresponding to the volume of computational cells with local pressure below the vapor pressure show a good agreement with the experimental result for suction-side TVC and pressure-side LE vortex cavitation to predict the intersection point of two curves. The numerical approach for predicting cavitation inception curves based on fully-wetted flow simulations in the behind-hull condition can be practically used for optimizing propeller designs to delay cavitation inception in a propeller design process.

References

- [1] ITTC. The specialist committee on cavitation induced pressure fluctuation: Final report and recommendations to the 22nd ITTC. Proc. of 22nd ITTC, Seoul/Shanghai, Korea/China, 1999.
- [2] S. Shin, J.W. Hong, D. Nagarathinam, B.K. Ahn and S.G. Park. Tip vortex cavitation and induced noise characteristics of hydrofoils. *Applied Sciences*, 11, 5906, 2021.
- [3] S. Berger, R. Gosda, M. Scharf, R. Klose, L. Greitsch and M. Abdel-Maksoud. Efficient numerical investigation of propeller cavitation phenomena causing higher-order hull pressure fluctuations. Proc. of 31st SNH, Monterey, CA, USA, 2016.
- [4] V. M. Viitanen, A. Hynninen, L. Lubke, R. Klose, J. Tantari, T. Sipila and T. Siikonen. CFD and CHA simulation of underwater noise induced by a marine propeller in two-phase flows. Proc. of SMP'17, Espoo, Finland, 2017.
- [5] K.W. Shin and P. Andersen. CFD analysis of propeller tip vortex cavitation in ship wake fields. Proc. of CAV2018, Baltimore, MD, USA, 2018.
- [6] N. Yilmaz, M. Atlar and P.A. Fitzsimmons. An improved tip vortex cavitation model for propellerrudder interaction. Proc. of CAV2018, Baltimore, MD, USA, 2018.
- [7] I. Park, J. Kim, B. Paik, H. Seol. Numerical study on tip vortex cavitation inception on a foil. *Appl. Sci.*, 11, 7332, 2021.
- [8] K.W. Shin and P. Andersen. Tip vortex cavitation suppression by tip modification of a ship propeller. Proc. of CAV2021, Daejeon, Korea, 2021.
- [9] K.W. Shin and P. Andersen. CFD analysis of ship propeller thrust breakdown. Proc. of SMP'19, Rome, Italy, 2019.

- [10] K.W. Shin and P. Andersen. Practical numerical method for erosion risk prediction on ship propellers. *International Shipbuilding Progress*, 67, 2020.
- [11] K.W. Shin, P.B. Regener, P. Andersen. Methods for cavitation prediction on tip-modified propellers in ship wake fields. Proc. of SMP'15, Austin, TX, USA, 2015.
- [12] B.W. McCormick. On cavitation produced by a vortex trailing from a lifting surface. *J. Basic Eng.*, 84(3) 1962.
- [13] K.W. Shin, P. Andersen, and R.M. Bering. CFD simulation on Kappel propeller with a hull wake field. Proc. of 16th Numerical Towing Tank Symp., Mulheim, Germany, 2013.
- [14] K.W. Shin and P. Andersen. Numerical study on characteristics of cloud cavitation on a ship propeller. Proc. of 3rd International Meeting on Propeller Cavitation, Istanbul, Turkey, 2018.